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A large, stylized logo consisting of a dark blue 'A' shape and an orange 'L' shape, partially overlapping.

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Carbon Tax and Emissions Transfer: a Spatial Analysis

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Abstract

With the rising role of globalization, assessing the impacts of carbon taxation on emissions embodied in trade becomes a key question. Our contribution consists of examining the effect of the carbon tax on emissions embodied in trade, in the framework of the input-output tables. We use variation in the economic sector of each country to first, identify the most and least polluting sectors, and second, investigate the spatial correlation due to carbon taxes in the emission embodied in trade using the SDA (structural decomposition analysis), MRIO (multi-regional input-output model), and spatial econometric models, for 56 sectors and 43 countries (32 OECD and 11 Non-OECD) from 2000 to 2014. Our findings show the “Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply” as the highest emitter sector. When the carbon tax is imposed in OECD countries, emissions embodied in exports (EEE) to and imports (EEI) from neighboring countries increase by 7.4 percent and 83.2 percent respectively, For Non-OECD countries, the results are 20.7 percent for exports and 79 percent for imports. Our policy recommendation is to coordinate the level of tax at least by region in order to avoid an increase in EEE.

Keywords: Carbon tax, Trade emission, multi-regional input-output table, Spatial econometric.

JEL codes: C31, Q20, Q43, Q56, R12, R15.

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1 Introduction

The Carbon Tax is the most recurring tool to decrease the figure of emissions (Kotlikoff et al., 2019). Accordingly, when there is growth in the carbon tax rate (like the environmental tax), carbon dioxide concentration will theoretically decline (Sundar et al., 2016). However, after implementing a carbon tax, countries tend to import carbon-intensive goods rather than produce them domestically with clean technology. To reduce trade costs such as fixed and variable costs of production, goods tend to be much more imported from neighboring countries, which are at low geographical distances and have strong trade partnerships (bilateral trade).

A carbon tax can affect neighboring nations (spatial impact) whenever there are tax differences between countries. Countries with lower taxes emit pollution at the national level when producing goods and services, and this pollution is transmitted to neighboring countries through emission embodied in exports (EEE). Since carbon taxes have increased in both OECD and Non-OECD countries, we would expect a convergence in terms of EEE. However, our results show that this is not the case (for further explanation, see Figure 1 in stylized fact).

Sakai & Barrett (2016) examines the empirical policy in line with the dwindling rate of CO₂ emissions in trade and links it to the international displacement of production. On the other hand, McEvoy & McGinty (2018) believes that offset emission abatement leads to even higher overall emissions, while Ren et al. (2020) disagree with this idea. Some scholars believe that input-output linkages play an important role in explaining the observed volatility of carbon emission embodied in trade (da Silva Freitas et al. (2016), Perobelli et al. (2015)). This model illustrates the volatility and interaction of direct and indirect emissions between intermediate sectors (for instance, "Electricity, gas, steam, and air conditioning supply") and final sectors.

According to the literature, environmental contamination exhibits striking spatial heterogeneity that is important for understanding the effects of policy. Due to spatial heterogeneity, environmental contamination in one country may have spillovers to neighboring countries. Currently, with the growth in international trade and the widening geographic separation between production and consumption, regional trade tends to be the core factor in transferring carbon emissions. Industrialized countries become net carbon importers while developing countries become net carbon exporters (Chen et al., 2016).

If we have differences between countries regarding the carbon tax, the price of intermediate inputs, and final requirements, companies may establish manufacturing processes in the area that is most cost-efficient for them. Hence, pollution is not only transferred from one country to another through trade, but also through differences in the prices of intermediate inputs and final requirements in different regions, differences in the prices of pollution for different goods, and the technology that each country uses for producing goods. This technology also affects the

level of pollution in the country itself and its neighboring countries.

Ignoring these effects can lead to biased estimators. Nevertheless, scholars barely discuss the influence of a carbon tax on trading emission embodied behaviors, while achieving compliance with commitments to reduce emissions is still debatable. Due to this, traditional panel models do not take into account the correlation between economic units and may provide estimated bias and inconsistent results (Elhorst, 2014).

For these reasons, we conduct our analysis while taking into account the spatial dependency between economic units, utilizing spatial econometric approaches (Anselin & Bera, 1998).

Despite the abundance of literature on carbon trading, our study contributes to the existing literature by filling a gap due to the uncovered analyze of the spatial effect of the carbon tax through EEE and emissions embodied in imports (EEI). In this regard, we first combine 65 intermediate and final sectors for 43 countries according to their ISIC code in the world input-output database (WIOD). Then, we implement the spatial impact of a direct and an indirect carbon tax on pollution stemming from export and import. The main feature of this study is that we examine the way pollution emitted from countries and sectors affects neighboring countries through economic and geographical perspectives.

To identify which sectors emit more pollution through intermediate and final goods, we merged data from 56 intermediate and into final sectors for 43 countries. The results, according to the literature (Wang et al., 2020), point to the "Electricity, gas, steam, and air conditioning supply" sector as the one emitting the most CO₂ into the environment (see Table 1 of the supplementary material). Regarding the effect of the carbon tax, OECD countries increase EEE and EEI by 7.4% and 83.2%, respectively, to and from neighboring countries, and in Non-OECD countries, the results are 20.7% for EEE and 79% for EEI.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the latest work in this field. Next, the estimation strategy and data are also shown in Section 3. Finally, Section 4 discusses the estimated results, and Section 5 is about the conclusions.

2 Literature review

In the first part of our theoretical model, we will concentrate on the composition effect highlighted by Antweiler et al. (2001). Managi et al. (2009) depicted how the composition of output (i.e., the structure of the intermediate inputs

and final requirements) influences emissions, which is determined by the volume of trade and the specialization linked to comparative advantage. Depending on the country's resource affluence and the strength of its environmental regulation, the composition effect could be good or bad. Copeland & Taylor (2013) and Antweiler et al. (2001) highlighted that the composition effect of trade for developing countries makes the environment more polluted, while this effect for developed countries makes them cleaner (Pollution Haven Hypothesis (PHH)). Thus, trade is bad for the environment since poor countries tend to be in developing processes, receiving international investment even for dirty production. On the contrary, the Porter Hypothesis (PH) contends that well-designed and stringent environmental regulations can stimulate innovation and benefit polluting countries by increasing firm productivity or the value of their products to consumers (Porter, 1996). Thus, as developed countries have higher income than developing countries, it is easier for developed nations to strengthen environmental regulation and adapt their production line to low-carbon technologies (technical effect). In other words, increasing environmental regulations in all countries (for example, imposing the same tax for all) raises the overall production cost of high-carbon goods. In this case, the manufacturing firm has to pay a fixed cost for settling the factory and producing processes, also a variable cost for transporting manufactured goods (imports). A carbon tax will increase both the fixed and variable costs of the plant. As a consequence, the comparative advantage of producing dirty goods in neighboring countries is reduced.

The second part of our work is based on the literature of Tobler (1979). According to Tobler's first geography law, countries are interconnected, but neighboring countries influence each other more than distant countries. Due to the lack of strong environmental regulations, some countries try to reduce their production costs by establishing factories in areas with weaker environmental regulations, importing high-carbon products, or exporting low-carbon products. Thus, neglecting the spatial dependency in an econometric analysis when variables are spatially linked will result in econometric estimations that are biased (Anselin & Bera, 1998).

Therefore, according to these hypotheses, the investigation of geographical and trade effects between countries is crucial because it shows that emissions are transferred among countries like a network. In this regard, we have some indicators: EEE and EEI. They are used to calculate the trade-embodied emissions that cause environmental impacts. The core model for estimating CO₂ emissions embodied in trade is input-output analysis (IOA). This model relies on emissions produced due to energy used in each intermediate consumption and production by sector (Ding et al., 2018). We then matched the corresponding exports and imports of goods and services (results are available upon request).

3 Empirical Strategy

In this section, we present our data and show summary statistics. We analyze 43 countries based on a spatial panel data model. Our data cover the 2000-2014 period.¹

3.1 Data

Table 1 illustrates the descriptive statistics of the variables. Statistical data were gathered for 43 countries (32 OECD and 11 Non-OECD countries).² The first column describes the short abbreviation of variables according to their definition in column two; column three indicates the unit of measurement, and the rest of the columns show statistical information. All the data were transformed into natural log before using them for analysis. Economic data such as intermediate inputs, final demands, and GDP per capita are in 2016 constant prices (US dollars).³

Table 1: Measurement and Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Variable	Definition	Unit	Data sources	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
EEE	Emissions embodied in exports	Mt	WIOD ⁴	3.084312	1.565002	0.1936106	7.440931
EEl	Emissions embodied in imports	Mt	WIOD	1.902461	0.4997026	0.5171322	2.99465
TAX	carbon tax	Million dollars	WIOD	12.28591	0.474615	10.42302	13.4406
TEAT	Total emissions with considering tax	mt	WIOD	9.579304	2.377294	4.020751	15.75208
IPI	The impact of tax on the price index	Million dollar	WIOD	3.4752	4.176509	-6.906018	16.12223
Clean-energy	The ratio of clean energy to total energy use	%	World bank	2.335806	1.175265	-2.438311	4.478425
PGDP	Per capita GDP	Million dollars	World bank	9.850114	1.032201	6.198263	11.53506
Intermediate-Local	Intermediate inputs in the local region	Million dollars	WIOD	12.33394	1.820735	7.795835	16.80984
Final-Local	Final requirements in the local region	Million dollars	WIOD	12.4209	1.803827	8.209721	16.64163
Intermediate-Other	Intermediate inputs in other regions	Million dollars	WIOD	11.15688	1.508922	7.028755	14.05075
Final-Other	Final requirements in other regions	Million dollars	WIOD	10.59018	1.583545	5.804292	14.00776
C-emission	Consumer Emissions	Million dollars	WIOD	3.403369	1.319361	1.026273	7.452639
P-emission	Producer Emissions	Million dollars	WIOD	3.654391	1.713101	-0.016084	8.134106
OECD	Belonging to an OECD country	Dummy Variable		0.744186	0.4366564	0	1

Source: Author’s calculation based on the dataset.

3.2 Stylized facts

3.2.1 Emission Embodied in Export (EEE), Emission Embodied in Import (EEI), and carbon tax

We plotted carbon tax, EEE⁵, and EEI⁶ in Figure 1 because the main question is whether the amount of carbon tax in each country has indeed reduced the amount of emissions embodied in trade in that country and other neighboring countries. In this figure, the carbon tax of both groups of countries shows a positive trend over time

¹In order to calculate the EEE, EEI, Carbon tax, and other independent variables, we were inspired by the papers Zhong et al. (2018) and da Silva Freitas et al. (2016). The method of calculating variables meticulously (explanatory and explained variables) is available upon request.

²The selection of OECD and Non-OECD countries was imposed by the availability of the WIOD data, also the highest pollution emitters per GDP per capita (see Table 5 of supplementary material).

³We have tested for cointegration. GDP per capita does not have a unit root. The null hypothesis (i.e., panels contain unit roots) is rejected. Therefore, GDP per capita is stationary (the result is available upon request).

⁵Emissions embodied in exports refers to the greenhouse gas emissions associated with the production of goods and services that are exported by a country.

⁶Emissions embodied in imports refers to the greenhouse gas emissions associated with the production of goods and services that are imported into a country.

and indicates that the carbon tax of OECD countries is higher than that of non-OECD countries. Even though the carbon tax is growing in both OECD and non-OECD countries, our results show no convergence in terms of EEE. It also illustrates that EEI from both groups of countries has experienced a flat pattern over time. Finally, our graph shows that with the increase of the tax, EEE has decreased over time in OECD countries, while this trend is slightly increasing in Non-OECD countries. In other words, to know more about the carbon tax changes in the 43 countries under review, as well as the EEE and EEI flow in the two top polluting countries (China and the US) at the beginning (2000) and end of the period (2014), see supplementary material.

Figure 1: The effect of Carbon tax, EEE and EEI in the OECD and Non-OECD countries

Source: Author's calculation

3.2.2 Coefficient of the Shares of Direct, Indirect and Total Carbon Emissions

The SDA (structural decomposition analysis) has the benefit of apprehending the direct and indirect impact taken through the Leontief matrix of the input-output tables (IOTs). In this section, we propose a structural decomposition analysis of the share of pollution in 56 sectors to assess the amount of emission in each industry. Subsequently, we highlight the more and less polluting sectors for CO₂. We merged the IOTs of the WIOD (World Input-Output Database) 2016 release with CO₂ of Environment Accounts. Therefore, we classified all sectors into 43 countries (31 OECD countries plus 12 major other countries). Then we examine the effects of pollution in each sector (see Table 1 in the supplementary material).

The results of total CO₂ emissions, the total output of various sectors, and the share of direct, indirect, and total carbon emission factors are shown in Table 1 of the supplementary material. Figure 2 shows the share of direct and indirect emissions of the most and least polluting sectors.

Considering the coefficient share of direct, indirect, and total emissions in the same year of different sectors the sector with the largest coefficient of direct, indirect, and total carbon emission for all years is "Electricity, gas,

steam, and air conditioning supply," while the sector with the smallest coefficient of direct, indirect, and total carbon emission for all years is "Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of households for own use."

The largest coefficients of the direct, indirect, and total emissions were 37.87 in 2012, 19.83 in 2007, and 42.93 in 2010, respectively, indicating an increasing trend of the inter-sectoral coefficient. The smallest coefficients for direct, indirect, and total emissions were 0.0058, 0.0026, and 0.0058 million tons of CO₂ in 2014, respectively. Thus, industries have continuously improved their production technology and energy use, and some sectors have achieved energy-saving and emission-reduction results due to increased attention paid to the environment.

Figure 2: Share of Direct and Indirect Emission in the most and fewer polluter sectors

Source: Author's calculation. Direct effects show how much pollution is produced in each sector. Indirect impacts indicate how much contamination is created by the intermediate products used in each sector's production. Total effects include all pollution from the production of goods themselves, whether the pollution comes from the production of goods or from the intermediate goods used in manufacturing.

3.3 Spatial model

We use various spatial tests to identify whether there is a spatial correlation between the data⁷. In this test, the significance of the statistics determines whether or not the non-spatial model can be rejected. We also check the log-likelihood function. We consider both lagged dependent and independent variables are considered. Not only is the value of emissions embodied in trade in a country related to the value of emissions embodied in trade in neighboring countries but also the values of independent variables in a country are related to the value of emissions embodied in trade in neighboring countries. We have chosen the SDM (Spatial Durbin Model) as the fitted model⁸. In the spatial Durbin model, the spatial effect of the explained variable and the explanatory variables are added to the conventional panel model.

⁷LM (Lagrange multiplier) test, LR (Likelihood Ratio) test, Wald test, and Moran MI Error Test

⁸SAR (Spatial Lag Model), SEM (Spatial Error Model), SDM (Spatial Durbin Model), and SAC (Spatial Autoregressive Model) are the models considered

Based on the theoretical and empirical literature, the final form of the SDM model for OECD and Non-OECD countries can be followed in Equation 1.

$$\begin{aligned} LnY_{ijt}^r &= \beta_0 + \rho W_{t-1}^{rs} LnY_{ijt}^r + \beta_1 \mathbf{T}_t^r + \beta_2 LnC_t^r + \beta_3 LnM_{ijt}^r + \\ &\delta_1 W_{t-1}^{rs} LnT_{ijt}^r + \delta_2 W_{t-1}^{rs} LnC_t^r + \delta_3 W_{t-1}^{rs} LnM_{ijt}^r + U_{ijt}^r + \epsilon_{ijt}^r \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Our outcome variables indicate both sides of imported and exported emissions, so it is common to use the same model for both estimations. Where:

- LnY_{ijt}^r is the dependent variable and can take alternatively the values:
 - $LnEEE_{ijt}^r$, the log of the emissions embodied in exports of products of sector i from sector j and country r in year t , i and $j = 1, \dots, 56$, for sectors, $r = 1, \dots, 43$, for countries, and $t = 1, \dots, 15$ for years,
 - $LnEEI_{ijt}^r$ the log of the emissions embodied in imports of product from sector i towards sector j and country r in year t ;

Our paper uses four groups of explanatory variables: Tax variables, Control variables, MRIO variables, and Dummy variables.

- The log of the Tax variables group is our main set of variables and includes the carbon tax, total emissions considering tax, and the impact of tax on price index variables. We calculated these variables based on da Silva Freitas et al. (2016) paper.

$$\beta_1 T_t^r = \beta'_1 LnTAX_t^r + \beta'_2 LnTEAT_{ijt}^r + \beta'_3 LnIPI_{ijt}^r$$

$$\delta_1 W_{t-1}^{rs} LnT_{ijt}^r = \delta'_1 W_{t-1}^{rs} LnTAX_t^r + \delta'_2 W_{t-1}^{rs} LnTEAT_{ijt}^r + \delta'_3 W_{t-1}^{rs} LnIPI_{ijt}^r$$

- $LnTAX_{ijt}^r$ is the log of the rate of a total carbon tax of the output in existing sector i from sector j in country r and year t ;
- $LnTEAT_{ijt}^r$ is the log of the total emissions before tax in sector i , sector j and country r and year t ;
- $LnIPI_{ijt}^r$ is the log of the impact of tax on the industrial price index for sector i and sector j and country r in year t ;
- W_{t-1}^{rs} is the spatial weight matrix between country r and its partner country s , measured by bilateral trade.

- The second set of control variables is as follows:

$$\beta_2 \text{Ln}C_t^r = \beta_1'' \text{LnClean.engi}_t^r + \beta_2'' \text{LnPGDP}_t^r$$

$$\delta_2 W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{Ln}C_t^r = \delta_1'' W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{LnClean.engi}_t^r + \delta_2'' W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{LnPGDP}_t^r$$

- $\text{LnClean} - \text{engi}_t^r$ is the log of the ratio of clean energy to total energy used in country r in year t .
- LnPGDP_t^r is the log of the GDP per capita for country r and year t ⁹.

- In the third set of our variables, we use the MRIO table from the WIOD to construct our dependent (EEE and EEI) and independent variables (intermediate inputs in the local region, final requirements in the local region, intermediate inputs in other regions, and final requirements in other regions). We use Zhong et al. (2018) paper to calculate them (our result is the same as theirs). The calculation of consumer and producer emissions variables is based on Kulionis (2014) paper.

$$\beta_3 \text{Ln}M_t^r = \beta_1''' \text{LnIntermediate.Local}_{ijt}^r + \beta_2''' \text{LnFinal.Local}_{it}^r + \beta_3''' \text{LnIntermediate.Other}_{ijt}^r + \beta_4''' \text{LnFinal.Other}_{it}^r + \beta_5''' \text{LnC.emission}_{ijt}^r + \beta_6''' \text{LnP.emission}_{ijt}^r$$

$$\delta_3 W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{Ln}M_{ijt}^r = \delta_1''' W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{LnIntermediate.Local}_{ijt}^r + \delta_2''' W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{LnFinal.Local}_{it}^r + \delta_3''' W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{LnIntermediate.Other}_{ijt}^r + \delta_4''' W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{LnFinal.Other}_{it}^r + \delta_5''' W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{LnC.emission}_{ijt}^r + \delta_6''' W_{t-1}^{rs} \text{LnP.emission}_{ijt}^r$$

- $\text{LnIntermediate} - \text{Local}_{ijt}^r$ is the log of the intermediate inputs of sector i to sector j used/produced in local region of country r in year t ;
- $\text{LnFinal} - \text{Local}_{it}^r$ is the log of the final demand for products of sector i ¹⁰ in the local region of country r in year t ;
- $\text{LnIntermediate} - \text{Other}_{ijt}^s$ is the log of the intermediate inputs of sector i to sector j produced in other regions of country s in year t ;
- $\text{LnFinal} - \text{Other}_{it}^s$ is the log of the final demand for products of sector i in other regions of country s in year t ;

⁹GDP does not have a unit root at the level. It rejects the null hypothesis (H0: panels contain unit roots). Therefore, the data is stationary at the level.

¹⁰over all Final consumption expenditure by households, Final consumption expenditure by non-profit organizations serving households (NPISH), Final consumption expenditure by government, Gross fixed capital formation, Changes in inventories and valuables

- $LnC - emission_{ijt}^r$ is the log of the consumer carbon emissions in sector i and sector j in county r and year t ;
- $LnP - emission_{ijt}^r$ is the log of the producer emissions of sector i and sector j in county r and year t .

When it comes to the variables:

- β_K , $K = 1, \dots, 12$ is the parameter of interest to be estimated;
- The spatial auto-regression coefficient would be explained by ρ ;
- β_0 is the constant term over time and fixed-effect to be estimated
- ϵ_{ijt} denotes an independent and identical distribution with zero mean and same variance;
- σ_0^2 ; U_{ijt} is the error term which captures all other omitted country factors, with $E(U_{ijt}) = 0$ for all i, j and t .

A spatial autoregressive term $\sum_{i=1}^n W_{t-1}^{rs} LnY_{ijt}^{rs}$ was included to estimate the spillover effects of carbon emissions of sectors i and j embodied in trade for a given couple of neighbor countries r and s in year t .

The impact of tax on emissions embodied in trade is estimated by four matrices (inverse squared distance, bilateral trade for 2013 (year $t-1$), export flow for 2013, and import flow for 2013). The geographic and economic matrices can be used to construct an instrument for emissions embodied in trade. This is what we do.

A spatial matrix based on geographical distance (Euclidean distance in kilometers between centroids of countries i and j) is used to illustrate the spatial contiguity. The two latter geographical matrices either use distance measurements to identify the proximity of countries or equal 1 when the countries are adjacent and 0 otherwise. Our geographical matrices are $1/d_{ij}^2$, $1/d_{ij}$, Queen, and Rook Contiguity. However, they are not a good fit for this study because most of the 43 countries in our study are spatially isolated. This may lead to a poor spatial regression model.

In this exercise, due to the fact that carbon emissions of countries inflow or outflow to their important trading partners, carbon emissions embodied in international trade may not only depend on geographic distance but also on the trading partners. An economic (bilateral trade) distance matrix is considered. The widely used gravity model for international exports and imports between two countries assumes that the unobservable multilateral resistance of each country might have an impact on other countries' trade (Qu et al., 2021) ¹¹.

Conspicuously, due to the simultaneity bias between explained and some explanatory variables (distance and trade), the spatial econometric panel models could not be estimated by ordinary least squares (OLS) (Long et al., 2016).

¹¹For more information on how to construct this matrix, see the working paper at <http://www.leo-univ-orleans.fr/fr/publications/documents-de-recherche-leo/dr-leo-2022.html>

4 Results Spatial Models

4.1 Spatial Autocorrelation Results

In this section, we present the results of our statistical tests and estimations for 32 OECD countries and 11 Non-OECD countries. Using a pooled panel model to assess the impact of emissions embodied in trade may result in biased decisions because this pollution includes spatial interactions that are not nested into standard panel models. To minimize bias and examine the spatial and spillover impacts of dependent and independent variables, we included the findings of various models, such as pool OLS, SAR, SEM, SDM, SAC, and GSPRE models, in this study to determine a suitable model.

We use Moran's I, spatial auto-correlation index, in the EEE and EEI models to detect potential spatial associations for 32 OECD countries and 11 Non-OECD countries, considering the trade matrix.¹² Spatial autocorrelation refers to the correlation between values of a variable and their close locational positions on a two-dimensional surface (Griffith, 1987). Neglecting spatial dependency in econometric studies can lead to biased estimates, as variables have spatial correlation (Anselin & Bera, 1998). As shown in Table 2, positive Moran's I values are found for EEE in OECD countries and EEI in both OECD and Non-OECD countries. The results of the spatial recognition tests indicate that the null hypotheses (lack of existence of spatial correlation) are rejected, and there is spatial autocorrelation in our application. **This means that there is strong and positive spatial autocorrelation in these models.** In general, emissions embodied in trade in one country can affect neighboring countries. However, the result of Moran's I in the EEE model for Non-OECD countries is not significant.

To represent the impact of the spatial dependency issue, LeSage & Pace (2009) presented a test that contained spatial lags for dependent variables and independent variables. Several tests can be considered to find a more appropriate model:

1. Likelihood ratio (LR) test is based on the log-likelihood function values of the various models.
2. Wald test.
3. Lagrange multiplier (LM) tests.

The spatial lag model (SAR¹³) and spatial error model (SEM¹⁴) are not nested. Therefore, Elhorst (2014) suggests that the classic LM-tests or the robust LM-tests proposed by Anselin & Bera (1998) can be used to find a more appropriate model. Acceptance of the LM (Lagrange multiplier) test shows that the hypothesis of no spatially lagged dependent variable and the hypothesis of no spatially autocorrelated error term are rejected. Also, when a robust

¹²The Moran index is sensitive to the type of matrix selected.

¹³The SAR model contains endogenous interaction effects.

¹⁴The SEM model involves the interaction effects among the error terms.

LM test is used, the null hypothesis of no spatially autocorrelated error term cannot be accepted. Both hypotheses (no spatially lagged dependent variable and no spatially autocorrelated error term) are firmly rejected for these models. The LM tests in Table 2 illustrate that the SEM model for the EEE model in OECD countries and the EEE model in Non-OECD countries, while the SAR model for EEI in OECD and EEE in Non-OECD are the best models.

Table 2: Spatial autocorrelation tests for EEE and EEI (Dependent variables: EEE and EEI; W: Wtrade2013)

Spatial tests	OECD		Non-OECD	
	EEE (Mt)	EEI (Mt)	EEE (Mt)	EEI (Mt)
Global Moran MI	0.8194***	0.1676***	-0.0065	0.7916***
LM Error (Burridge)	368.3192***	15.4096***	0.0037	54.787***
LM Error (Robust)	432.6812***	1.8727	48.2029***	132.7823***
LM Lag (Anselin)	2.6511	21.7261***	6.1886**	9.3014***
LM Lag (Robust)	67.0131***	8.1892***	54.3878***	87.2967***

Source: Author's calculation. Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01, respectively. We decided to use the "trade matrix for the year 2013" as the spatial weight

SDM contains SAR and SEM models, so we need to compare these two models with the SDM model using the Wald tests.¹⁵ As shown in Table 3, these null hypotheses are rejected, so the SDM model is accepted. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) calculates the amount of lost information by a model, while the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) maximizes a model's posterior probability given the data (Burnham & Anderson, 2002). The better model is the one with the lower AIC. Four alternative model specifications are examined based on the aforementioned analysis: no fixed effects model, spatial fixed effects model, time-period fixed effects model, and spatial and time fixed effects model. Based on the result of the log-likelihood ratio in these models, the spatial and time-fixed effects model is chosen for both OECD and Non-OECD countries in EEE and EEI.

Table 3: Wald test and Log-likelihood ratio for spatial and time fixed effects model (Dependent variables: EEE and EEI; W: Wtrade2013)

	OECD		Non-OECD	
	EEE (Mt)	EEI (Mt)	EEE (Mt)	EEI (Mt)
AIC	-2412.788	-2632.233	-666.908	-838.5455
BIC	-2312.617	-2532.062	-592.3654	-764.0028
Wald SAR va SDM	33.77***	21.29**	20.1**	70.91***
Wald SEM va SDM	28.18***	18.11**	17.66*	68.23***
Log-likelihood	1230.3939	1340.1166	357.454	443.2728

Source: Author's calculation. Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01, respectively.

We calculate log-likelihood statistics and corrected R-squared statistics to compare the five distinct spatial weight matrices (Queen and rook contiguity, inverse distance, inverse distance square, and trade matrix for the year 2013). In the EEE model, the group of OECD countries has the largest log-likelihood value (1279.075) for the inverse distance matrix, but the trade matrix for the year 2013 has the largest corrected R-squared of 0.5377. Also, in the EEE model, the group of Non-OECD countries has the largest log-likelihood value (373.3158) and the largest corrected R-squared of 0.1624 for the inverse distance square matrix.

¹⁵The Wald test for SAR model via SDM model tests the null hypothesis that spatial autocorrelation occurs only if the host country influences the neighboring countries. The Wald test for SEM model via SDM model tests the null hypothesis that spatial autocorrelation occurs only if the error value of a host country has an influence on the error values of neighboring countries.

In the EEI model, the group of OECD countries has the largest log-likelihood value (1359.6508) for the rook contiguity matrix, but the Queen contiguity matrix has the largest corrected R-squared of 0.7951. Likewise, in the EEI model, the group of Non-OECD countries has the largest log-likelihood value (467.4925) for the inverse distance matrix and the largest corrected R-squared of 0.0571.¹⁶ Our result is similar to that of Zhong et al. (2018), since it is common that countries have an influential effect through their mutual borders. To sum up, we decide that the best matrix in this research for EEE and EEI in OECD and Non-OECD countries will be the trade matrix for 2013.

4.2 Spatial Analysis Result

Based on the MRIO, average EEE, average EEI, and average environmental tax can be obtained (see Table 5 in the supplementary material). Columns (1), (3), (5), and (7) in Table 4 are based on a simple panel pool OLS model. They allow us to see how biased estimation results are if spatial relationships are ignored. Actually, SDM models in Table 4 illustrate the dependencies in the spatial relationships between a dependent variable and independent variables, concerning bilateral trade in the year t-1 matrices (columns (2), (4), (6), and (8)).¹⁷

According to Table 4, carbon tax, total emissions after-tax, IPI (The impact on price index)¹⁸, intermediate inputs, and final requirements in the other regions, and producer emissions concerning the trade matrix have a positive, significant effect and expected sign, while the ratio of clean energy to total energy use, intermediate inputs, and final requirements in the local region have a negative, significant effect and expected sign on the EEE in OECD countries. Specifically, carbon tax, GDP per capita, and final requirements in local and other regions, consumer and producer emissions concerning the trade matrix have a positive effect. IPI and intermediate inputs in local and other regions have a negative effect on EEI in OECD countries, respectively.

Carbon tax, the ratio of clean energy to total energy use, and consumer and producer emissions have a positive sign, while intermediate inputs in local and other regions have a negative sign on EEI in Non-OECD countries. We do not have spatial effects in EEE of Non-OECD countries, so we interpret the simple traditional model. In this model, carbon tax, intermediate inputs in other regions, and consumer and producer emissions have a positive effect, but the ratio of clean energy to total energy use, GDP per capita, and intermediate inputs in local regions have a negative effect on EEE in Non-OECD countries.

With an increase in the carbon tax, the output and input prices of products grow, particularly for energy

¹⁶Results of all models are available upon request.

¹⁷We estimated the equation for the inverse distance matrix, inverse distance square matrix, Queen contiguity matrix, Rook contiguity matrix, and bilateral carbon tax matrix as well. Results are available upon request.

¹⁸To calculate the IPI, refer to the paper by (da Silva Freitas et al., 2016)

products. Thus, if some sectors reduce the amount of investment, importing goods will become more competitive, and imports will increase. For OECD countries, the amount of tax increases, but for some rich sectors, this amount is not fair enough and cannot be filled with the amount of exports, so OECD countries pay permission for pollution and continue to produce dirty goods, and then export this pollution to the neighboring area. An increase in total emissions after tax due to incorrect environmental policies leads to EEE for OECD countries.

The ratio of clean energy to total energy use (Clean-engi) indicates that using clean technologies is expensive for sectors of OECD and Non-OECD countries. So, if they are obliged to use this technology, their demand will decrease, which will lead to a decline in EEE. These results are in line with Zhong et al. (2018), while using clean technologies in Non-OECD countries increases the desire of rich countries to buy clean goods at a low cost, thus increasing EEI.

The magnitude of carbon emissions embodied in trade is influenced by the level of GDP per capita (PGDP) during industrialization. Carbon emissions flow into OECD and flow out of Non-OECD countries, confirming the findings of Xu & Dietzenbacher (2014).

When the local economy produces all the intermediate inputs itself, the pollution from the transportation of these goods through trade (whether through imports or exports) is reduced in the OECD and Non-OECD countries, as found by Zhong et al. (2018) and Xu & Dietzenbacher (2014).

The final requirement in the local region (Final-Local, some sectors in IOTs sell some of their output to local consumers) has positive effects on emissions inflows in OECD and Non-OECD countries, and negative effects on carbon emissions outflows in OECD countries, as found in Zhong et al. (2018) and Xu & Dietzenbacher (2014).

In regard to Zhong et al. (2018) and Xu & Dietzenbacher (2014), intermediate inputs in other regions (Intermediate-Other, where some sectors in IOTs sell some of their output to other sectors in other regions) have a negative effect on emissions inflows and a positive effect on carbon emissions outflows.

The coefficient of the Final requirement in other regions (Final-Other, where some sectors in IOTs sell some of their output to consumers in other regions) has a positive impact on emissions inflows in OECD countries and outflows from both OECD and Non-OECD countries, which confirms the findings of Zhong et al. (2018) and Xu & Dietzenbacher (2014).

Producer emissions indicate that carbon dioxide emissions calculated from the consumer perspective are significantly higher than producer emissions, as highlighted by Ren et al. (2020), de Boer et al. (2019), and Elliott et al.

(2010).

The IPI index represents the purchasing power losses for consumers after the implementation of tax policy. It has a negative effect on EEI and a positive effect on EEE.

Table 4: OLS and SDM spatial and time fixed effects model (Dependent variables: EEE and EEI; W: Wtrade2013)

	OECD				Non-OECD			
	OLS	SDM	OLS	SDM	OLS	SDM	OLS	SDM
	EEE (Mt)	EEE(Mt)	EEI(Mt)	EEI(Mt)	EEE(Mt)	EEE(Mt)	EEI(Mt)	EEI(Mt)
Columns	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Tax	-0.0110	0.0738***	0.733***	0.832***	0.207***	-0.0488	0.911***	0.790***
	(-1.16)	(5.84)	(50.93)	(72.92)	(3.38)	(-0.96)	(41.13)	(23.56)
Teat	0.00202	0.00922**	0.00663	-0.00199	0.00765	0.0171	0.0239**	-0.00169
	(0.31)	(2.67)	(0.69)	(-0.64)	(0.32)	(1.79)	(2.78)	(-0.28)
IPI	0.000110	0.0803***	0.00101	-0.0555**	0.00305	0.247***	0.00468*	0.0263
	(0.06)	(4.12)	(0.36)	(-3.16)	(0.48)	(3.65)	(2.02)	(0.63)
Clean-engi	-0.0168***	-0.00981*	0.0182***	-0.00333	-0.100***	-0.0140	-0.0158**	0.0183**
	(-5.90)	(-2.22)	(4.24)	(-0.83)	(-6.03)	(-1.50)	(-2.63)	(3.09)
PGDP	0.0191**	-0.00845	0.00931	0.0712***	-0.126***	-0.185***	0.00579	0.0306
	(3.03)	(-0.38)	(0.98)	(3.53)	(-6.98)	(-3.31)	(0.89)	(0.88)
Intermediate-Local	0.0409*	-0.100***	-0.441***	-0.282***	-0.189**	-0.0808	-0.332***	-0.373***
	(2.23)	(-5.85)	(-15.92)	(-18.30)	(-3.27)	(-1.16)	(-15.83)	(-8.59)
Final-Local	-0.126***	-0.134***	0.130***	0.0966***	-0.0992	-0.978***	0.0885**	-0.0230
	(-7.29)	(-5.07)	(4.97)	(4.07)	(-1.33)	(-10.74)	(3.28)	(-0.40)
Intermediate-Other	0.0122	0.0685***	-0.0421	-0.136***	0.155***	-0.0430	-0.0555***	-0.0889***
	(0.83)	(5.04)	(-1.89)	(-11.10)	(3.63)	(-1.10)	(-3.60)	(-3.67)
Final-Other	0.0963***	0.0441***	0.0312	0.0423***	0.151***	0.0995**	-0.0791***	0.0311
	(8.87)	(3.76)	(1.90)	(4.02)	(5.47)	(3.04)	(-7.94)	(1.53)
C-emission	0.454***	-0.0307	0.282***	0.268***	0.401***	0.148*	0.0380	0.245***
	(24.16)	(-0.98)	(9.92)	(9.51)	(6.01)	(2.20)	(1.58)	(5.58)
P-emission	0.565***	1.072***	0.193***	0.154***	0.630***	1.676***	0.342***	0.290***
	(24.85)	(24.05)	(5.63)	(3.85)	(9.02)	(14.90)	(13.51)	(4.16)
W*Tax		0.127	0.132	0.0328		0.0328	0.0353	
		(1.61)	(1.21)	(0.33)		(0.33)	(0.42)	
W*Teat		0.0155	0.0164	-0.0178		-0.0178	0.00175	
		(1.22)	(1.45)	(-0.44)		(-0.44)	(0.07)	
W*IPI		0.0103	0.0192	0.308		0.308	0.0919	
		(0.13)	(0.27)	(1.58)		(1.58)	(0.75)	
W*Clean-engi		-0.0333	-0.0606**	-0.0860		-0.0860	0.0967*	
		(-1.55)	(-3.10)	(-1.14)		(-1.14)	(2.05)	
W*PGDP		-0.500***	-0.0939	-0.129		-0.129	-0.185	
		(-4.44)	(-0.93)	(-0.55)		(-0.55)	(-1.28)	
W*Intermediate-Local		-0.116	-0.243**	0.160		0.160	-0.290**	
		(-1.16)	(-2.65)	(0.98)		(0.98)	(-2.78)	
W*Final-Local		0.0350	0.0137	-0.288		-0.288	0.213	
		(0.33)	(0.15)	(-0.56)		(-0.56)	(0.68)	
W*Intermediate-Other		-0.0987	-0.0737	-0.0766		-0.0766	0.0458	
		(-1.48)	(-1.20)	(-1.05)		(-1.05)	(1.02)	
W*Final-Other		0.0962	0.0540	0.135		0.135	0.0236	
		(1.61)	(1.00)	(1.93)		(1.93)	(0.54)	
W*C-emission		-0.349**	-0.151	0.0652		0.0652	-0.0166	
		(-3.27)	(-1.23)	(0.22)		(0.22)	(-0.09)	
W*P-emission		0.743**	0.362*	-0.217		-0.217	-0.0879	
		(2.97)	(2.06)	(-0.30)		(-0.30)	(-0.20)	
ρ		-0.205	-0.0915	-0.0299		-0.0299	-0.160	
		(-1.63)	(-0.71)	(-0.16)		(-0.16)	(-1.50)	
σ^2		0.000303***	0.000246***	0.000754***		0.000754***	0.000291***	
		(17.22)	(13.05)	(8.38)		(8.38)	(7.95)	
Constant	-0.672***		-4.993***		-1.532**		-6.555***	
	(-6.26)		(-30.78)		(-2.81)		(-33.21)	
Number of observation	480	480	480	480	165	165	165	165

Source: Author's calculation. Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01, respectively. Data in the parenthesis is the t-statistic.

Changes in the dependent variable related to the main independent variable are important, but paying attention to the alteration value in the neighboring countries and home country can also be the crucial cause of EEE and EEI (LeSage & Pace, 2009). In this regard, calculating the marginal effect tends to be the most effective method of accurate explicit. We are interested in knowing not only the direct effects of a carbon tax on a host country's economy but also the indirect effects on its neighbors.

In Table 3, an increase in a country's tax, total emissions with consideration of tax, the impact of tax on price index, intermediate input in other regions, final requirements in other regions, or producer emissions is associated with a statistically significant (1% level) increase in its own EEE of OECD countries. On the contrary, the ratio of clean energy to total energy use, intermediate inputs in the local region, and final requirements in the local region decrease the EEE of OECD countries. Also, by increasing the carbon tax, GDP per capita, final requirements in local and other regions, consumer and producer emissions increase, but the impact of tax on price index, and intermediate inputs in local and other regions decreases in their own EEI of OECD countries. Specifically, when carbon taxes are implemented, the ratio of clean energy to total energy use, consumer emissions, and producer emissions increase, whereas intermediate inputs in local and other regions decrease in their own EEI of non-OECD countries.

In other words, the GDP per capita and consumer emissions of a host country have negative effects, but producer emissions have a positive effect on the EEE of neighboring countries (indirect effect or spillover) in the OECD countries. An increase of 1% in the ratio of clean energy to total energy use and 1 million dollars in intermediate input in the local region in the OECD countries cause a decrease of 5.7% and 20.1% of these variables, respectively, in neighboring countries. Considering the impact of EEI in non-OECD countries, an increase of 1% in the ratio of clean energy to the total energy use of the home country causes an increase of 8.5% in the ratio of clean energy in neighboring countries. A decrease of 1 million dollars in the intermediate input in the local region results in a rise of 19.8% in the intermediate input in the neighboring region when the impact of EEI in non-OECD countries is taken into account.

On the whole, regarding EEE, when the carbon tax, producer emissions, and final requirements in other regions are increased by 1 million US dollars, in OECD countries, they are raised by 16.9%, 11.7%, and 150.5%, respectively. In contrast, the ratio of clean energy to total energy use, GDP per capita, intermediate input in the local region, and consumer emissions all lead to a decrease in EEE in OECD countries. Additionally, an increase of 1 million dollars in the carbon tax and producer emissions of OECD countries results in growth of 88.8% and 47.8% in EEE, respectively. Conversely, when the ratio of clean energy to total energy use is increased, intermediate inputs in local and other regions will increase by 5.98%, 48.1%, and 19.4%, respectively, leading to a decrease in EEI in OECD countries. Overall, we find that an increase in trade between countries' independent variables (carbon tax and the ratio of clean energy to total energy use) is associated with a statistically significant (1% level or better) increase in EEI. The total effect is due to the fact that if we increase intermediate input in the local region, it decreases EEI.

Table 5: Direct, Indirect and Total effects (Dependent variables: EEE and EEI; W: Wtrade2013)

Columns Variable	OECD						Non-OECD					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
	Direct effect	Indirect effect	total effect	Direct effect	Indirect effect	total effect	Direct effect	Indirect effect	Total effect	Direct effect	Indirect effect	Total effect
Tax	0.0723*** (5.55)	0.0965 (1.47)	0.169** (2.58)	0.332*** (70.36)	0.0555 (0.86)	0.888*** (13.45)	-0.0473 (-0.90)	0.0382 (0.36)	-0.00906 (-0.07)	0.795*** (23.43)	-0.0778 (-1.28)	0.717*** (10.41)
Test	0.00888** (2.62)	0.0112 (1.02)	0.0201 (1.74)	-0.00226 (-0.74)	0.0148 (1.46)	0.0126 (1.17)	0.0169 (1.78)	-0.0196 (-0.50)	-0.00271 (-0.07)	-0.00197 (-0.32)	0.000825 (0.04)	-0.00114 (-0.06)
IPI	0.0822*** (4.49)	-0.00131 (-0.02)	0.0809 (1.08)	-0.0540** (-3.24)	0.0267 (0.39)	-0.0273 (-0.36)	0.254*** (3.79)	0.316 (1.50)	0.571* (2.47)	0.0277 (0.68)	0.0843 (0.77)	0.112 (0.97)
Clean-ongi	-0.00939* (-2.16)	-0.0274 (-1.50)	-0.0368* (-2.06)	-0.00292 (-0.76)	-0.0569** (-3.09)	-0.0598** (-3.28)	-0.0137 (-1.34)	-0.0863 (-1.15)	-0.1000 (-1.30)	0.0155** (2.60)	0.0853* (2.03)	0.101* (2.41)
PGDP	-0.000817 (-0.04)	-0.426*** (-3.88)	-0.427*** (-3.74)	0.0720*** (3.70)	-0.0957 (-1.02)	-0.0237 (-0.24)	-0.188*** (-3.35)	-0.136 (-0.54)	-0.324 (-1.22)	0.0359 (1.06)	-0.172 (-1.30)	-0.136 (-1.01)
Intermediate-Local	-0.0985*** (-6.12)	-0.0772 (-1.01)	-0.176* (-2.19)	-0.281*** (-18.95)	-0.201* (-2.34)	-0.481*** (-5.30)	-0.0828 (-1.22)	0.179 (1.13)	0.0963 (0.54)	-0.367*** (-8.71)	-0.198* (-2.16)	-0.565*** (-5.59)
Final-Local	-0.134*** (-4.98)	0.0507 (0.57)	-0.0835 (-0.84)	0.0970*** (3.97)	0.00222 (0.02)	0.0992 (0.99)	-0.980*** (-9.85)	-0.268 (-0.47)	-1.248* (-2.04)	-0.0285 (-0.47)	0.205 (0.71)	0.177 (0.59)
Intermediate-Other	0.0698*** (5.26)	-0.0953 (-1.61)	-0.0255 (-0.43)	-0.137*** (-11.48)	-0.0576 (-0.95)	-0.194** (-3.13)	-0.0457 (-1.31)	-0.0810 (-0.99)	-0.127 (-1.30)	-0.0922*** (-4.33)	0.0524 (1.29)	-0.0398 (-0.81)
Final-Other	0.0436*** (3.89)	0.0730 (1.39)	0.117* (2.33)	0.0427*** (4.32)	0.0459 (0.89)	0.0886 (1.71)	0.102*** (3.43)	0.138 (1.75)	0.241** (2.67)	0.0320 (1.77)	0.0184 (0.48)	0.0505 (1.18)
C-emission	-0.0240 (-0.75)	-0.298** (-3.16)	-0.322*** (-3.49)	0.270*** (9.37)	-0.173 (-1.63)	0.0965 (0.90)	0.150* (2.05)	0.0418 (0.14)	0.191 (1.403)	0.248*** (5.08)	-0.0602 (-0.36)	0.188 (1.18)
P-emission	1.060*** (23.56)	0.445** (2.71)	1.505*** (8.91)	0.149*** (3.66)	0.329 (1.81)	0.478* (2.53)	1.673*** (14.21)	-0.270 (-0.35)	1.403 (1.76)	0.289*** (4.17)	-0.136 (-0.34)	0.152 (0.37)

Source: Author's calculation. Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01, respectively. Data in the parenthesis is the t-statistic.

Regarding the robustness tests, we tested for serial correlation (autocorrelation), heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, and stationarity. We found that in all situations, the results remained unchanged, and spillovers had a positive effect. Thus, all results are fairly robust. Firstly, we checked the Structural Break test for the 2008 financial crisis to examine whether our results are robust after splitting our sample into two periods, before and after the financial crisis. Following this, we found that there were no breaks for the EEE and EEI models in OECD and non-OECD groups of countries. Our results are robust to all of these specifications. The models could be affected by GDP per unit of energy consumption in country r from country s in year t and GDP growth, but it seems these variables are not significant. To consider the unobserved heterogeneity, we estimated the time, fixed country-level, time and fixed effect in the pool, and spatial effects. So, we did not include them in our final results (results of robustness tests are available upon request).

5 Conclusions

Our research explores the impact of carbon taxes on emissions embodied in trade for 43 countries over the period 2000-2014. At the sector level, the sector [Electricity, gas, steam, and air conditioning supply] has the highest direct, total, and indirect emissions of CO₂, while the sector [Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of households for own use] has the lowest direct, indirect, and complete emissions of CO₂.

In this study, we find that the increase in the price of the tax leads to an increase in the amount of CO₂ emitted in exports and imports in both OECD and non-OECD countries (Table 4). Using the trade matrix (comparative advantage), we find that when we increase the carbon tax by one million US dollars, pollution by imports in OECD and non-OECD countries increases by 83.2 percent and 79 percent, respectively. Furthermore, when we increase the carbon tax by one million US dollars, pollution by exports in OECD and non-OECD countries increases by 7.4 percent and 20.7 percent, respectively.

We also find that not taking into account the spatial effect of environmental tax policy on exports and imports of pollution increases pollution on exports. Considering the large amount of emission embodied in exports by the investigated countries, we suggest reducing the export flow of local high energy-consuming products as a priority. This target can be achieved by raising their prices, reducing the capacity of heavy industry, or increasing the taxation of such products.

5.1 Policy Recommendations

The majority of pollution is contributed to the electricity section. Therefore, when making an efficient policy, attention must be given to this department.

Governments should take into account the environmental taxation in their country and their neighbors. Developing countries produce goods that are consumed by developed countries, but carbon emissions are charged to their national accounts. As a result, the consumption price of goods is higher (and can even become prohibitive) in importer countries compared to exporter countries. The best strategy for controlling emissions would be to impose the same carbon tax in all the countries which produce such goods and services.

Converging to the same tax price is beneficial to all countries or regions. Countries producing more carbon than others tend to be more reluctant to impose emission prices at the same level as those that pollute less. If none of the countries accept the carbon tax law and they go on polluting, the transmission of pollution to neighboring countries through trade or poor coordination increases pollution at the global level.

Carbon tax rises EEE from the country that rises the tax to their neighbors. We should be cautious when analyzing also the comparative advantage of the countries because this could have an effect on increasing EEE and EEI due to dirty specializations. The production of dirty goods should be left to a country with highly clean technology.

6 Declarations

6.1 Funding

This work was supported by Campus France and the Institute Kurde de Paris. Sahar Amidi has received research support from Campus France and the Institute Kurde de Paris.

6.2 Competing Interests

Financial interests: Rezgar Feizi, Thaís Núñez Rocha, and Isabelle Rabaud declare they have no financial interests. Sahar Amidi has received travel support from the University of Orleans (LEO).

6.3 Availability of data and materials

The data and codes of the paper are available upon request after the publication of the paper.

6.4 Author Contributions

Isabelle Rabaud and Thaís Núñez Rocha contributed to the guidance and editing. Rezgar Feizi contributed to some parts of the model. The draft of the manuscript, study conception, some parts of the model, editing, material preparation, data collection, and analysis were performed by Sahar Amidi. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

6.5 Ethics approval

This declaration is not applicable.

6.6 Consent to participate

This declaration is not applicable.

6.7 Consent to publish

This declaration is not applicable.

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A Appendix A: review of literature and several statistics

Table A1: Average of Share of Direct, Indirect and total Carbon Emission in 56 sectors in period 2000-2014

Sectors (%)	Avrg. SDIE	Avrg. SDE	Avrg. SIE
Accommodation and food service activities	1.0085	1.7829	0.8152
Activities auxiliary to financial services and insurance activities	0.0660	0.1260	0.0512
Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of households for own use	0.0101	0.0338	0.0041
Administrative and support service activities	0.6233	0.9790	0.5344
Advertising and market research	0.0673	0.1274	0.0525
Air transport	2.1608	0.4740	2.5848
Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis	0.1529	0.2493	0.1289
Computer programming, consultancy and related activities; information service activities	0.1941	0.3540	0.1542
Construction	3.7363	10.9150	1.9514
Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	2.0730	2.0882	2.0668
Education	0.7048	1.2010	0.5793
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	36.1142	16.0849	41.3520
Financial service activities, except insurance and pension funding	0.3116	0.6422	0.2287
Fishing and aquaculture	0.1353	0.1227	0.1385
Forestry and logging	0.1787	0.1313	0.1905
Human health and social work activities	1.1135	1.7035	0.9678
Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding, except compulsory social security	0.1495	0.2505	0.1243
Land transport and transport via pipelines	3.3623	2.0953	3.6806
Legal and accounting activities; activities of head offices; management consultancy activities	0.3833	0.6894	0.3067
Manufacture of basic metals	7.6422	7.5154	7.7015
Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	0.2151	0.6819	0.0987
Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products	4.3873	4.7543	4.2878
Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products	3.2098	3.3799	3.1630
Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products	0.6531	1.7708	0.3751
Manufacture of electrical equipment	0.6259	1.9187	0.3115
Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	1.0465	3.0020	0.5720
Manufacture of food products, beverages and tobacco products	1.8728	3.6333	1.4306
Manufacture of furniture; other manufacturing	0.7956	0.8434	0.7850
Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.	0.9803	2.5391	0.6000
Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	0.8945	2.4454	0.5148
Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	6.5343	3.0331	7.4058
Manufacture of other transport equipment	0.2715	0.6405	0.1821
Manufacture of paper and paper products	0.8162	1.2091	0.7155
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products	1.8628	1.8215	1.8708
Manufacture of textiles, wearing apparel and leather products	0.8583	1.5905	0.6728
Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials	0.3128	0.6114	0.2373
Mining and quarrying	3.6344	4.0934	3.5087
Motion picture, video and television programme production, sound recording and music publishing activities; programming and broadcasting activities	0.0663	0.1793	0.0379
Other professional, scientific and technical activities; veterinary activities	0.1303	0.2195	0.1081
Other service activities	0.8393	1.3060	0.7217
Postal and courier activities	0.1038	0.1718	0.0871
Printing and reproduction of recorded media	0.1773	0.3522	0.1333
Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	2.2297	2.8758	2.0680
Publishing activities	0.0654	0.1879	0.0350
Real estate activities	0.7143	2.0513	0.3788
Repair and installation of machinery and equipment	0.0650	0.1541	0.0433
Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1.1124	1.8166	0.9346
Scientific research and development	0.1278	0.2191	0.1050
Sewerage; waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery; remediation activities and other waste management services	0.7277	0.4644	0.7937
Telecommunications	0.2495	0.6603	0.1459
Warehousing and support activities for transportation	0.5000	0.8093	0.4259
Water collection, treatment and supply	0.2347	0.5708	0.1504
Water transport	2.0035	0.6625	2.3407
Wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	0.2745	0.4648	0.2269
Wholesale trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1.2199	2.4264	0.9186

source: Author's calculation

Avrg. SDIE: Average share of direct and indirect emission, Avrg. SDE: Average share of direct emission,

Avrg. SIE: Average share of indirect emission

B Appendix B: Sectoral deviation

Table A2: Source of Variables

Short name of Variable	Full Name	Definition	Source
EEE	Emissions embodied in exports		WIOD
E EI	Emissions embodied in imports		WIOD
TAX	Carbon tax	Carbon taxation tries to replace trading as the international system of carbon emissions reduction	OECD
TEBT	Total emissions before tax		WIOD
TEAT	Total emissions after tax	After emission tax is inflicted, the output and input prices of products, particularly energy sector products, will grow	WIOD
IPI	The impact of tax on price index	Implementation of the tax policy could be measured by a general price index that explains the purchasing power losses for consumers	WIOD
GDP-engi	GDP per unit of energy consumption	Unit of energy consumed to generate the amount of GDP in a country	World Bank
Clean-engi	The ratio of clean energy to total energy use	Coal-oil-gas-dominated fossil fuel mix produces a lot of carbon emission in production processes	World Bank
PGDP	Per capita GDP	global trade expands, rapid economic growth is stimulating to speed up global industrial transfer and thus is influencing carbon emissions embodied in the trade all over the world	World Bank
Intermediate-Local	Intermediate inputs in local region	In international trade, foreign capital, and energy inflows are the main sources of intermediate inputs, and thus affect carbon emissions flows	WIOD
Final-Local	Final requirements in the local region	For one country, each sector in this country would import other regions' final goods and services as final requirements to meet the needs of the local region through international supply chains in the process of globalization	WIOD
Intermediate-Other	Intermediate inputs in other regions		WIOD
Final-Other	Final requirements in other regions		WIOD
C-emission	Consumer Emissions	Carbon dioxide emissions calculated from the consumer perspective are significantly higher than producer emission	WIOD
P-emission	Producer Emissions	Carbon dioxide emissions calculated from the producer	WIOD

Table A3: The abbreviated name

SDA: structural decomposition analysis	NBER: National Bureau of Economic Research
WIOT: input-output tables semi-closed model with eight household groups	FGLS: Feasible Generalized Least Squares
SNA: System of National Accounts	CAS: Chinese Academy of Sciences
SUT: Supply and Use Tables	CEAD: China Emissions Accounts and Datasets
SAM: Social Accounting Matrix	AGEIS: Australian Greenhouse Emissions Information System
SRIO: single region input-output tables	FTA: free trade agreement
BTIO: bilateral trade input-output model	CGER: Center for Global Environmental Research and NIES: National Institute for Environmental Studies
NEEBT: net CO ₂ emissions embodied in bilateral trade	SWIID: Standardized World Income Inequality Database
TEAM: Trade and Environmental Assessment Model	BEA: Bureau of Economic Analysis
LMDI: Logarithmic Mean Divisia Index	NBS: Chinese National Bureau of Statistics
BEETI: net balance of emissions embodied in trade in intermediates and BEETT: total trade	IBGE: Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics
	GTAP: Global Trade Analysis Project
	EIA: Energy Information Administration
	NEI: National Emissions Inventory
	EPA: US Environmental Protection Agency
	TATP: terrestrial Air temperature and Precipitation

Table A4: Results of Correlation Between Variables

	eee	eei	tax	teat	ipi	Clean-engi	pgdp
eee	1.0000						
eei	0.5991	1.0000					
tax	0.3965	0.8068	1.0000				
teat	0.8722	0.6431	0.4224	1.0000			
ipi	0.3728	0.1298	0.2325	-0.0445	1.0000		
Clean-engi	-0.0144	-0.0364	0.0263	0.0212	0.0707	1.0000	
pgdp	0.0798	0.1982	0.1939	0.0723	0.0576	-0.2019	1.0000

source: Author's calculation

Table A5: The average of emission embodied in export and import and carbon tax for 2000-2014

Country	code	Avrg. EEE	Avrg. EEI	Avrg. TAX
OECD countries				
Australia	aus	50.79661029	9.100313894	334939.2825
Austria	aut	16.87145772	4.78817513	169857.421
Belgium	bel	26.70316959	6.733997406	227325.7726
Canada	can	77.42223962	9.930795687	328071.7398
Switzerland	che	31.93633507	13.4707526	507579.9839
Czech Republic	cze	11.32190979	9.832361325	382795.4924
Germany	deu	187.2075815	10.22514275	172529.3409
Denmark	dnk	19.83211694	14.60837769	475024.1392
Spain	esp	76.53173737	7.978346119	237446.9336
Estonia	est	1.446026998	3.534826698	128072.2366
Finland	fin	13.47380777	5.939058782	204179.0076
France	fra	145.2721137	10.92329685	294799.9472
United Kingdom	gbr	150.9824349	10.04602783	233780.409
Greece	grc	15.75064801	8.777150406	248781.8225
Croatia	hrV	3.445970831	5.391066601	174672.6566
Hungary	hun	8.5499836	5.075583774	162115.0068
Ireland	irl	14.45984527	4.566584099	161584.4152
Italy	ita	121.8244872	7.458692595	196982.3691
Japan	jpn	341.377003	10.41410861	336847.5793
Korea	kor	61.11263879	5.765567267	220699.6308
Lithuania	ltu	2.755810508	6.499920479	230467.2752
Luxembourg	lux	4.373176512	4.010898099	191516.3626
Latvia	lva	1.446396662	2.941455918	98821.63649
Mexico	mex	67.01969549	13.30514272	362564.6796
Netherlands	nld	44.05544836	8.772824038	266586.7741
Norway	nor	17.61302392	13.16354475	469120.937
Poland	poL	23.05830908	9.020108196	294499.6161
Portugal	prt	13.74342209	7.681996705	244926.1209
Slovak Republic	svk	4.582316301	3.166756661	106778.8683
Slovenia	svn	2.832002482	2.472011484	81544.05095
Sweden	swe	25.14665704	2.700137703	60205.74821
Turkey	tur	32.91277511	6.049291437	197488.8777
United States	usa	967.2983209	15.56530284	322899.9893
Non-OECD countries				
Bulgaria	bgr	2.17809311	3.330447939	129886.802
Brazil	bra	76.60627786	12.10296251	385732.7709
China,P.R.: Mainland	chn	244.280833	5.871437106	242564.4881
Cyprus	cyp	1.973679085	7.927001601	246856.0368
Indonesia	idn	27.78529771	4.881528734	169493.7236
India	ind	71.64263714	6.866056988	220110.5998
Malta	mlt	2.058060405	4.998654184	176644.3062
Romania	rou	7.746212091	8.451783142	290224.5888
Russian Federation	rus	45.43840377	5.360620206	172111.5847
Tanzania	TZA	27.40866477	4.858258195	186566.8085

source: Author's calculation

B.1 EEE, EEI, and Carbon tax

The geo-maps illustrate how much emissions are embodied in exports in top countries like China and the United States emitted to different countries (imports) and also show the changes in carbon tax intensity throughout the 43 countries over the period shown, for 2000 and 2014. Obviously, for both years, the figure of a carbon tax in this group of countries studied increased considerably from 8,334 billion dollars in 2000 to 10,622 billion dollars at the end of the period. In addition, for both the USA and China, they emitted more pollution into Brazil in 2000 than they did into Brazil in 2014, while Mexico for the USA in 2014 and Brazil for China in both 2000 and 2014 being the most contaminated destinations.

As indicated in Figure 3 to Figure 6, for spatial transfer of the EEE in 2000, countries classified by the higher net export of embodied CO₂ emissions are the USA, China, Germany, Japan, the UK, and France, whereas the wealthiest countries, such as Norway, Denmark, Brazil, Mexico, Canada, and Switzerland, had the highest net emissions embodied in import of CO₂ over the period shown.

Figure 4 also depicts the amounts of emissions gap between export and import from 2000 to 2014. It demonstrates that identifying the main emitter of emissions in this study cannot be impossible. We are unable to specify the most emission-importing countries due to the constraint of the input-output table; in other words, the wealthiest importer is not clear to us. Generally, we can say that the countries with the highest CO₂ importers tend to be developing nations.

Specifically, the highest carbon emissions (exceeded from 100 Mt) stem from the USA and China to Brazil in 2000 and Mexico and Brazil in 2014, respectively. Although this figure for the USA went down from 1704.24 to 634.11 between 2000 and 2014, China is the only country that emitted more CO₂ than the 42 other countries from 203.91 to 631.11 over this period. Moreover, in 2000, the top countries which transferred more CO₂ to other countries were the USA, Japan, Germany, the UK, France, and China, whereas the USA, China, Japan, Germany, the UK, and France took the lead in 2014. Countries like the USA, Norway, Mexico, Denmark, and Brazil had the highest net import of embodied CO₂ emissions in 2000, respectively, while Denmark, the USA, Norway, Brazil, and Mexico were ahead in 2014.

Figure 1: The effect of Carbon tax, EEE and EEI in the USA 2000

Source: Author's calculation

Figure 2: The effect of Carbon tax, EEE and EEI in the USA 2014

Source: Author's calculation

Figure 3: The effect of Carbon tax, EEE and EEI in China 2000

Source: Author's calculation

Figure 4: The effect of Carbon tax, EEE and EEI in China 2014

Source: Author's calculation

Figure 5: GAPS Between EEE and EEI

Source: Author's calculation

The line graphs in Figure 5, compare the amounts of total estimated tax for both OECD and Non-OECD countries with emissions embodied in export and import from 2000 to 2014. Overall, the figure for estimated tax for both countries has an upward trend between 2000 and 2014. Except for the EEE of Non-OECD countries, other lines (EEE and EEI) have a downward trend over the period shown. Total tax emissions for OECD countries increased steadily from 700 in 2000 to just over 900 in 2010 before declining significantly to 800 at the end of the period, while at the beginning, EEE declined from just under 450 to 170 in 2007 and then maintained the same level until 2014. In comparison, EEI moderately go down during the next 15 years. In 2000, for Non-OECD countries EEE decreased from 260 to somewhere in the vicinity of 200 in 2002, then don't changes between 2003 and 2007. Following this, there was a dramatic growth to 650 in 2014. By contrast, EEI experienced a slight decline during this period.

Figure 6: The effect of Carbon tax, EEE and EEI in the countries under study

Source: Author's calculation

The gap tax between total real tax and estimated tax in this study comes from the usage of equation 14. In this function, the environmental carbon tax is equal to the inverse of the output matrix which multiplied the emission coefficient for each sector in each country by the carbon tax coming from the activity sector, this indicates the amount of emission tax from each sector in each country.

The Figure 6 shows the gap between estimated tax and real tax from 2000 to 2014. Overall, the figure for a gap between estimated tax and real tax was initially almost as high as real tax (around 1,000 billion dollars). However, while both increased between 2000 and 2004, the former despite moderate fluctuation maintained the same level until 2014, and the latter increased slightly until hitting a peak of 12,000 billion dollars in 2011 and then unchanged through the remained period.

Total estimated tax during the whole of the period as much higher than, and has a striking resemblance in movement with the figure for the gap between estimated tax and real tax.

Figure 7: GAPS Between estimated Carbon tax and real tax (billion dollars)

Source: Author's calculation

C Appendix C: The Tide Methodology of MRIO

C.1 Emissions Embodied in Bilateral Trade (EEBT) and the Multi-Regional Input-Output (MRIO)

The Input-Output (IO) method analysis can be used to measure the direct and indirect (complete) economic impacts of carbon emissions. This method also examines the interdependence between production factors, including intermediate input and final requirements within a specific activity or sector. As a result, it enables the calculation of both direct and indirect environmental impacts of products, providing a quantitative estimation of pollutants. By using this model, it is possible to accurately determine regional and inter-regional GHG emission rates, as well as evaluate the inter-linkages between different sectors. Consequently, the IO method analysis is recognized as a powerful tool for estimating changes in pollution.

Two essential methods are used to calculate pollutant emissions: the EEBT and the MRIO models. The EEBT model evaluates pollutant emissions in bilateral and inter-regional trade, while the MRIO model identifies links between international industries to estimate pollutant emissions along global supply chains. Both models consider trade in both intermediate inputs and final goods and services.

The EEBT method is commonly used to measure the scale of pollution embodied in inter-regional trade (S. Wang et al. (2019); B. Zhang et al. (2016)). In contrast, the intermediate demand coefficient (A) matrix in the MRIO model only includes domestic components. In the EEBT method, intermediate exports are added as column vectors along with final demand to provide a more comprehensive picture of pollutant emissions.

The MRIO model is a useful tool for analyzing how different economic sectors respond to changes in the final demand for goods and services within a national economy over a given period. The core of this model is the Input-Output Tables, which represent the trading connections between industries (intermediate consumption) and households (final consumption) expressed in price. The model considers both the inter-regional connections between multi-regional units and their evolution over time.

The MRIO approach utilizes three types of data: each region's input-output table, each region's export level to the world, and each region's CO₂ emissions data. It enables researchers to measure inter-regional trade volumes of various goods and describe economic ties between regions and sectors in depth. The model is widely preferred by scientists for its ability to analyze the trade-related carbon relations between different countries or regions.

For example, separate studies have shown that the energy market is the most significant source of pollution, followed by household and government consumption. To mitigate CO₂ emissions, governments should introduce initiatives that facilitate public investment in the form of green consumption, such as constructing public green buildings S. Guo et al. (2020); Su et al. (2017) and Su & Thomson (2016).

Z. Zhang & Hewings (2014) proposed a methodology to compute the pollution haven hypothesis using the EEBT method, which investigates the consequences of direct trade without considering inter-regional feedback impacts. As such, the EEBT method is only partially a consumption-based method. In contrast, the MRIO method takes into account the entire inter-regional supply chain, including relevant spillover and feedback impacts. Several studies have extensively used the MRIO method to investigate China's region-specific greenhouse gas and other environmental emissions (B. Zhang et al. (2016), Zhao et al. (2016), Xie et al. (2015), Lv et al. (2019), F. Wang et al. (2017), Li et al. (2016), Chen & Fath (2015)).

Since our focus is on inter-regional relations and the impact of pollution on neighboring countries/regions, we will rely on the MRIO model.

In the input-output approach, $Z_{ijt}^{r,s}$ represents the intermediate transfers from sector i in region r produced to meet the needs of sector j in region s in year t , where $r, s = 1, 2, \dots, 43$ and $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 56$ ($i \neq j, r \neq s$). $A_{ijt}^{r,s}$ represents the direct consumption coefficient (the Leontief coefficient). According to input-output theory (Miller and Blair, 2009), the equilibrium among the column and row in the input-output table is demonstrated as:

$$X_r^r = \sum_{s=1}^N Z_r^{rs} u + \sum_{s=1}^N F_r^{rs} \quad (1)$$

The matrix F_r^{rs} represents the final demand for each region, which can be expressed uniformly using the matrix notation $X_t = Z_t u + F_t u$ or alternatively as $X_t = A_t X_t + F_t u$.

Carbon emissions VE_t can be assumed as follows:

$$\mathbf{VE}_t = \begin{pmatrix} (W_t^1)' M_t^{1,1} & \dots & (W_t^1)' M_t^{1,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ (W_t^n)' M_t^{n,1} & \dots & (W_t^n)' M_t^{n,n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where $VE_{i,t}^{r,s}$ is the coefficient of the total carbon emission, expressing the total quantity of the direct and indirect CO₂ released by the output of the production sector i , in year t and region r , s (the unit of measure is tons). It can be obtained as follows: $w_{i,t}^r = e_{i,t}^r / X_{i,t}^r$, with $e_{i,t}^r$ being an element of the matrix that describes the volume of CO₂ emissions per unit of GDP for each sector in each region. Each element in this matrix is then divided by the final output of each sector.¹

Where $M_t^{r,s} = (1 - A_t)^{-1}$ represents the coefficient of total relationships between regional sectors; It is a Leontief inverse matrix (Wassily, 1986).

With all of the equations above we can accurately measure the total CO₂ emissions (see equation 3) and distinguish between carbon emissions created by the demand of the region r for the local production of the region r , and emissions embodied in exports from the region r towards region s in year t , (see equation 4, where $r, s \in N, N=1, 2, \dots, 43$).

$$E_{r,t}^T = E_{r,t} + E_{r-s,t} \quad (3)$$

$$E_{r,t} = \left[\sum_{k=1}^N (v_t^{kr})' \right] f_t^{rr} \quad (4)$$

¹Source: Our World in Data

$$E_{r-s,t} = \left[\sum_{k=1}^N (v_t^{kr})' \right] f_t^{rs} + (v_t^{rs})' \left(\sum_{k=1}^N f_t^{rk} \right) \quad (5)$$

Where $E_{r-s,t}$ represents the CO₂ emissions embodied in exports, i.e., emissions from the final product exported from region r to another consuming region. $\sum_{k=1}^N (v_t^{kr})'$ is a row vector of CO₂ emissions created in all regions that are required for (and thus embodied in) one unit of the final commodity produced in a particular sector k in region r . f_t^{rs} defines, for each sector, the final goods and services produced in region r for the final users of another region s . The term $(v_t^{rs})'(\sum_{k=1}^N f_t^{rk})$ shows the amount of CO₂ emissions from an intermediate good produced in region r that is sent to other economic sectors for production in other regions. Emissions embodied in trade (EET) for any region r consist of emissions embodied in imports (EEI) and emissions embodied in exports (EEE) (Serrano & Dietzenbacher, 2010), which are expressed as follows:

$$EEE_r = \sum_{s \neq r}^N EEP_{r-s} = \left[\sum_{k=1}^N (v_t^{kr})' \right] \left(\sum_{s \neq r}^N f_t^{rs} \right) + \sum_{s \neq r}^N \left[(v_t^{rs})' \left(\sum_{k=1}^N f_t^{rk} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

$$EEI_r = \sum_{s \neq r}^N EEP_{s-r} = \sum_{s \neq r}^N \left[\sum_{k=1}^N (v_t^{kr})' \right] f_t^{sr} + \left[\sum_{s \neq r}^N (v_t^{sr})' \right] \left(\sum_{k=1}^N f_t^{rk} \right) \quad (7)$$

Using equation 6 and equation 7, we can calculate the amount of pollutant emission generated from exports and imports. Furthermore, these equations allow us to determine the proportion of pollutant emission from exports of the region r to other regions, identify the source of the pollutant present in a particular region, and find the difference between the emissions from bilateral trade (J. Guo et al. (2018) and Zhong et al. (2018)).

In equation 6 and equation 7, EEP_{r-s} and EEP_{s-r} show emissions embodied, respectively, in export and import from regions r to region s .

Then, the trade balance of CO₂ emissions embodied is used as a representation to explain the "carbon leakage" between region r and region s (Peters & Hertwich, 2008). It can be expressed as follows:

$$E_{r,t}^{BEE} = EEE_{r,t} - EEI_{r,t} \quad (8)$$

As stated by Peters & Hertwich (2008), the total production emissions inventory can be expressed as equal to

emissions from trade, as follows:

$$E_{r,t}^{P-emission} = EEE_{r,t}^T \quad (9)$$

Similarly, the consumption emission inventory is measured as the total emissions from production minus the balance of CO₂ emissions embodied in trade:

$$E_{r,t}^{C-emission} = EEE_{r,t}^T - EEI_{r,t}^{BEET} \quad (10)$$

C.2 Tax

In the literature on input-output tables, two price models allow for measuring the impact of price changes on the whole economy: the Ghosh and Leontief price models (Ghosh (1958); Leontief (1941) and Leontief (1966)). These models show the effect of variations in the price of intermediate production on economic sectors and the final price value of production factors in consuming activities (Georgescu-Roegen (1951) and Ghosh (1958)). The purpose of this research is to measure the impact of green taxes on emissions. It assumes that green taxes lead to fluctuations in production expenditure, which in turn induce an increase in prices. According to the pricing model, the demand for final and intermediate products is the essential factor of price setting (da Silva Freitas et al. (2016) and Phungrassami & Usubharatana (2019)). The prices, weighted by the ratio of the sum of input expenditure to the value-added, can be expressed as equation (11):

$$X_{i,t}^r = i' AX_t^{rr} + (V_{i,t}^{r,s})' \quad (11)$$

If the value-added vector and each element of the matrix A represent monetary values, then the value-added raw vector v describes the monetary value of output in terms of value-added. To solve equation 12, we multiply the coefficients of the matrix A by a price vector P , as defined in equation 14, using post-multiplication. Given that $(I - A)^{-1} = L$, we can then derive the solution as follows:

$$P_t^r = (I - A')^{-1} V_t^{u,r} = (L_t^{r,s})' V_t^{u,r} \quad (12)$$

If the government were to institute a uniform tax on the volume of CO₂ emissions across all productive sectors, including industrial activity, the resulting tax vector T can be represented by the following equation:

$$T_t^r = \varphi_t^r V E_t^{r,s} x_t^{r,r} \quad (13)$$

Let φ denote the CO₂ emission rate per ton from all polluting sectors in region r , and let $x_t^{r,r}$ represent the final output of all sectors in region r .

The total emission tax rate for the output can thus be calculated as follows:

$$\tau_t^r = T_t^r (x_t^{r,r})^{-1} \quad (14)$$

The implementation of a carbon tax provides insight into the potential impact of environmental policies on the economy, industries, and emissions. However, the effects of such taxes vary among countries due to differences in product and demand structures, making it difficult to generalize their impact (da Silva Freitas et al., 2016). Additionally, the regressive effects of emissions taxes can vary among activities and manufacturing firms, as the tax rate differs across sectors and countries. It should be noted that the following analysis does not account for any increase in prices due to taxes, and the adjusted price vector is as follows:

$$\tilde{P}_t = (L_t^{s,r})' (V_t^r + \tau_t^r) \cdot \tilde{p}_t - \tilde{P}_t^r \quad (15)$$

As previously mentioned, the total emissions intensity in the absence of a carbon tax can be expressed by the equation relating to each sector: $V E_{i,t}^r = e_{i,t}^r / X_{i,t}^r$, where $e_{i,t}^r$ is a vector representing total sector emissions and $X_{i,t}^r$ indicates the total output of industrial activities.

According to Gemechu et al. (2014), the tax may also lead to variations in sectoral output prices, which could affect the total output of productive sectors. To estimate such impacts, it is assumed that the monetary values of output without and with the carbon tax remain constant. Therefore, the change in output for sector j following the introduction of the tax (X_j) can be calculated as follows:

$$X_{j,t=1}^r = \frac{\tilde{P}_{t=0}^r}{\tilde{P}_{t=1}^r} X_{j,t=0}^r \quad (16)$$

Let $P_{t=0}^r$ denote the price index for the base year, and let $P_{t=1}^r$ represent the new price index after the inclusion of the tax. The total emissions following the implementation of the tax can be estimated as follows:

$$e_{i,t}^r = (M_t^{r,s})' \cdot X_{j,t=1}^r \quad (17)$$

Let $X_{j,t=1}^r$ denote the new final output and $(M_t^{r,s})'$ represent the total coefficient relationships between sectors, which is a Leontief inverse matrix.

The impact on the Industrial Price Index (IPI) can be expressed as follows:

$$IPI_t = \sum_{j=1}^{43} \tilde{P}_t a_{t,j} \quad (18)$$

Here, $a_{t,j}$ represents the technical coefficient that reflects the ratio of intermediate consumption of industry j product to the total output (da Silva Freitas et al., 2016).

C.3 Direct and indirect effects

When examining the matrix of partial derivatives of the dependent variable, changes in the dependent variable under certain conditions (known as the direct effect, represented by every diagonal element of the matrix) may also lead to changes in other dependent variables under different conditions (known as the indirect effect, represented by every off-diagonal element). Consequently, the direct and indirect effects can vary depending on the situation in question within the sample, as noted by LeSage & Pace (2009) and Elhorst (2014). For example, due to differences in geographical distance, the impact of emissions embodied in exports on the host country may differ from that of its neighboring countries.

$$\left[\begin{array}{ccc} \frac{\partial E(Y)}{\partial x_{1k}} & \dots & \frac{\partial E(Y)}{\partial x_{Nk}} \end{array} \right]_t = (I - \delta W)^{-1} [\beta_{1k} I_N + \beta_{2k} W] \quad (19)$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{ccc} \frac{\partial E(Y)}{\partial x_{1k}} & \dots & \frac{\partial E(Y)}{\partial x_{Nk}} \end{array} \right] = [(1 - \tau)I - (\delta + \eta)W]^{-1} [\beta_{1k} I_N + \beta_{2k} W] \quad (20)$$

Equations 19 and 20 display the mathematical formulas for the direct and indirect effects of changes in explanatory variables on the dependent variable Y in the short and long term, respectively. Equation 19 indicates that indirect effects do not occur when $\delta = 0$ and $\beta_{2k} = 0$, while Equation 20 shows that indirect effects do not occur when

$\delta = -\eta$ and $\beta_{2k} = 0$ (Elhorst, 2014). In order to measure the effect of emissions embodied in trade before and after taxation in the host country and neighboring countries, we calculate both the direct and indirect effects of each exogenous variable in our study.

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_4 LnM_t^{rs} + \delta_9 \sum_{ij=1}^n W_{ij} LnM_{ijt}^{rs} = & \beta_6 LnIntermediate.Local_{ijt}^{rs} + \beta_7 LnFinal.Local_{ijt}^{rs} + \\ & \beta_8 LnIntermediate.Other_{ijt}^{rs} + \beta_9 LnFinal.Other_{ijt}^{rs} + \beta_{10} LnC.emission_{ijt}^{rs} + \beta_{11} LnP.emission_{ijt}^{rs} + \\ & \delta_6 \sum_{ij=1}^n W_{ij} LnIntermediate.Local_{ijt}^{rs} + \delta_7 \sum_{ij=1}^n W_{ij} LnFinal.Local_{ijt}^{rs} + \\ & \delta_8 \sum_{ij=1}^n W_{ij} LnIntermediate.Other_{ijt}^{rs} + \delta_9 \sum_{ij=1}^n W_{ij} LnFinal.Other_{ijt}^{rs} + \\ & \delta_{10} \sum_{ij=1}^n W_{ij} LnC.emission_{ijt}^{rs} + \delta_{11} \sum_{ij=1}^n W_{ij} LnP.emission_{ijt}^{rs} \end{aligned}$$

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